

Data Reuse: comparing the principles

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Abstract

Government and commercial organisations have accrued vast amounts of data over years of investment. This data is worth billions of pounds but is not being reused. The ability to reuse data could deliver better value from the initial investment that has been made by allowing an organisation to use their resources more efficiently potentially saving time and money. The overall goal of the work reported here is to identify and investigate the current state of play with respect to impediments to data reuse considering both the technical and social aspects of the problem. This paper focuses on the principles that have been suggested as necessary to facilitate an ecosystem where data is reused by addressing the research question *how do the different sets of principles suggested compare and what role does policy play?* Common themes and principles are identified, that when combined, could be used as the basis for a set of principles that are agnostic to sector or the type of data.

Keywords – data reuse; data sharing; principles; policy

1 Introduction

The way data is designed, captured, and managed comprises approaches primarily intended for single use purposes resulting in huge amounts of data being generated. Government and commercial organisations have accrued vast amounts of data over years of investment which is worth billions of pounds but is not being reused. Data reuse could deliver better value from the initial investment that has been made (by government or private sectors). The ability to reuse data could allow an organisation to use their resources more efficiently potentially saving time and money.

Resources (i.e., platforms, policies, and search tools) that have been developed to facilitate data reuse such as The European Open Science Cloud (European Commission, 2017), DataCite (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019), and the UK Data Service's ReShare ('The UK Data Service.

ReShare', 2021), typically focus on scientific or research data and are often not designed for use by a wider audience.

Funded by the Alan Turing Institute and the Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (Dstl), the project "Investigating the Problem of Data Reuse" (Wood and Bordoloi, 2023), identified the current state of play with respect to the impediments to data reuse considering both the technical and social aspects of the problem. The project produced two systematic literature reviews (one for each aspect), a mapping between the two perspectives, and an interdisciplinary research agenda (Wood and Bordoloi, 2023).

The systematic literature reviews helped understand the state-of-the-art identifying key themes, applications, and research projects in addition to any challenges that are still to be addressed. The search phrases "data reuse", "reusing data" and "data sharing" were used to identify an initial set of literature where these phrases appeared in the title, abstract or keywords. To be in scope, papers had to: be open access, written in English, be published in the last five years (i.e., 2017-2022), be available in Scopus or Web of Science, and be US or UK based. These requirements helped scope the project and ensure it could be completed on time. Further work would see some of these requirements expanded (e.g., consider more than the last five years and consider more countries).

The literature review identified seven papers that each proposed a set of principles necessary to facilitate an ecosystem where data is shared and reused. This paper compares the principles and explores the role that policy plays. The comparison has identified nine common themes and an additional five principles that would be applicable to a wider audience than they were originally intended. When combined, these could be used as the basis for a set of principles that are agnostic to sector or the type of data.

A brief overview is given of each of the seven papers (section 2), followed by a review of the principles that were proposed (section 3). The paper concludes with a discussion

of the role that policy plays in moving towards an ecosystem where data is intended to be shared and reused (section 4).

2. The literature being considered

Of the seven papers that were identified as presenting a set of guidelines or principles, four papers focused on clinical or health related data (Callaghan, 2020; Cole *et al.*, 2021; Corpas *et al.*, 2018; Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018). The remaining papers focused on a sector (i.e., engineering (Dodds *et al.*, 2020)); or, a particular community (the Interactive Information Retrieval (IIR) community (Gäde *et al.*, 2021) and statisticians (Ellis and Leek, 2018)).

Callaghan (2020) presents an overview of a report (“Recommendations and Guidelines on data sharing”), that was produced by the Research Data Alliance COVID-19 Working Group (2020). The group comprised over 440 members, from different backgrounds, and had the goal of delivering a set of guidelines and recommendations on how to share data, across disciplines, to inform responses to a pandemic. The proposed guidelines are divided into four research areas (social sciences, clinical, omics and epidemiology), and four cross cutting themes (research software, legal and ethical considerations, community participation and indigenous data). The split is designed to help users easily find what is most relevant to them. A set of “foundational elements” are also included that are common to the different research areas. The foundational elements are grouped into challenges and recommendations. A differentiation is made between guidelines (detailed advice on the practice of sharing data or software) and recommendations (generic advice that is at a much higher level).

Cole *et al.*, (2021) present a set of ten principles that would allow the responsible sharing of clinical data; it is intended that others could build on what has been proposed. The proposed guidelines are intended for academic medical, not-for-profit organisations. The underlying goals of the principles are to share within “minimum necessary” (i.e., only share the elements that are needed); maintain the trust of patients whilst facilitating any innovation that may come from sharing; and, ensure original investigators can continue to make the most of any research opportunities that may arise from the reuse of their data.

Focusing on the providers of human genomic data, Corpas *et al.*, (2018) propose a set of five guidelines, referred to as tips, that would maximise a human genomic dataset’s ‘FAIRness’ (where FAIR refers to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles (Wilkinson, 2016)). The work by Corpas *et al.*, (2018) is based on the authors own experiences of using Repositive (a platform that holds a catalogue of shared human genomic datasets).

Tenenbaum and Blach (2018), focus on the reuse of derived datasets for patients with Alzheimers. Four publicly available datasets are examined to establish the degree to which they adhere to the FAIR principles. The FAIR principles focus on the machine-readability of a dataset. Based on the examination, a set of criteria are proposed, additional to the FAIR principles that would help promote data sharing when considering human users.

Dodds *et al.*, (2020) present a set of nine principles to improve data accessibility within engineering and related sectors. The proposed principles should be considered as a “manifesto for change” to facilitate a data ecosystem where the value of data is maximised for the different stakeholders whilst mitigating any potential harms. The nine principles highlight the overlaps and gaps in existing policy initiatives and programmes. The manifesto also includes recommendations for different stakeholders (i.e., government, academia, privacy sector, founders, professional bodies).

Gäde *et al.*, (2021) aim to provide a resource for the Interactive Information Retrieval (IIR) community that will aid documenting and archiving research. Eight principles are proposed for the reuse of resources, with a five-level system architecture showing “concrete steps” on how the principles can be achieved. The work aligns with the FAIR principles but is focused on challenges that are faced by the IIR community. Research is considered to comprise three types of resource: research design (“the methods and techniques used to collect and analyse the empirical data”), research infrastructure (“provides access to the IIR system”) and research data (“any data that is collected, observed, generated or created during or as a result of the research process”). Gäde *et al.*, (2021) consider reuse as a broad term that covers the use of any of the three resource types for more than one purpose. The eight principles are visualised in a graphic. Core to the principles are *knowledge* and *terminology*. The remaining principles distinguish between those that focus on the individual researcher (*plan, document, publish*) and those aimed at the wider IIR community (*require, reward*).

Ellis and Leek (2018) propose a set of guidelines for sharing data with someone who must process or analyse that data (i.e., a data scientist, statistician, or analyst) but has not been involved in its collection. The aim of principles is to make the handover more efficient and reduce any possible errors or delays in analysis due to the data recipient not having a full understand of the data. If a statistician is to be able to process the data without any additional cleaning or processing, they will require the raw data, information regarding any data processing that has already taken place and information regarding the experimental conditions. All

data and information should be presented in a clear and consistent format.

3. Comparing the principles

Although the proposed principles focus on different sectors, users and types of data, there are some common themes. These themes could be used as the basis for a set of principles that are agnostic to sector or the type of data. Some of the principles that were found in only one or two of the papers (i.e., not common themes) would be applicable to a wider audience than they were originally intended and could therefore also be considered for inclusion in a more general set of principles.

3.1. Common themes

Nine themes have been identified through a review of the eight papers and the principles that they propose: infrastructure, resourcing, planning, documentation, governance, stewardship, storage, incentives, and FAIRness.

Infrastructure

Infrastructure is a key component of a data sharing ecosystem. A focus on shared data infrastructure would help ensure and maintain quality, security, access to data and increase the adoption of standards (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). The infrastructure must support the management, curation, discovery, analysis and visualization of the data (Kjærgaard *et al.*, 2020). Some considered data as infrastructure itself, which would require maintenance in a similar way any physical infrastructure would (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). Investment in infrastructure should take advantage of economies of scale (Callaghan, 2020).

Resourcing

As noted by Gäde *et al.*, (2021), resources could include research design, the infrastructure and the data itself. Data sharing is more than just putting information online, resources are required to make it sustainable (Kjærgaard *et al.*, 2020). Ideally, dedicated resources are required to facilitate data sharing, especially if trying to adhere to the FAIR principles (Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018).

Planning

Data sharing and data reuse will only be possible if it is planned for. Data management planning must occur at the early stages of the research (Callaghan, 2020), before any data is collected and begin with a documented Data

Management Plan (DMP) (Gäde *et al.*, 2021). Planning should consider the whole data lifecycle (Gäde *et al.*, 2021).

Documentation

Through a survey of users, Kjærgaard *et al.*, (2020) identify the largest barriers to using shared open data as knowing what datasets are available and a lack of documentation (Kjærgaard *et al.*, 2020). Documentation plays a crucial role in facilitating an ecosystem where data can be shared and reused. The five-level system architecture that is presented by Gäde *et al.*, (2021), to show how their set of principles can be achieved, focuses on documentation. If a resource is well-documented it is more likely that it can be reused without the need for any repeat in the research leading to a focus on innovation and discovery of knowledge (Gäde *et al.*, 2021).

If society is to benefit from the maximum value of the data, all research resources should be documented in as much detail as possible (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). This includes the code, models, guidance, insights as well as the data. Where available, standardised and machine-readable documentation formats should be adopted (Gäde *et al.*, 2021). The documentation should put both the data and the research into context (Callaghan, 2020). Metadata should be specified using standards that allow researchers from outside the domain community to understand the data (Callaghan, 2020). Metadata should also document the data's provenance (Corpas *et al.*, 2018) and the different versions of the data (Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018). How the data has been collected, the conditions of the experiment, any limitations on reuse based on any participant consent forms should be included in the documentation (Corpas *et al.*, 2018). The machine-readability of the data and the metadata should be maximized to increase the findability and interoperability of the dataset (Corpas *et al.*, 2018).

Governance

Data governance processes will have to be in place to ensure data is collected, processed and stored ethically, responsibly and comply to any legal requirements (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). Within a data sharing ecosystem, that should include constraining how the data will be shared and who can access it (Corpas *et al.*, 2018). This could be done via data sharing consent frameworks (Corpas *et al.*, 2018) or data sharing agreements (Cole *et al.*, 2021). Data sharing agreements should have defined time limits and it should be possible to revoke access to the data at any time (Cole *et al.*, 2021).

As Corpas *et al.*, (2018) note, data sharing consent frameworks vary (according to country, funder and study) and it would be useful if existing standards for digital consent formats could be adopted to ensure interoperability.

Callaghan (2020) notes the need for coordination across jurisdictions.

If participant data is to be shared beyond the project for which it is collected, this should be made clear with the potential risks and benefits to the participants specified (Corpas *et al.*, 2018). Suitable “representative stakeholders” should oversee all decisions about data sharing (Cole *et al.*, 2021).

Stewarding

Data must be stewarded (i.e., responsibly managed). When stewardship is done well, data is discoverable and accessible (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). Poor stewardship would occur when it is not clear on the rights and responsibilities of those in charge of managing the data. (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). Cole *et al.*, (2021) state that stewardship should be specified by the data sharing agreement and data ownership should be non-transferable.

Storage

Research resources should be archived and published using long-term, open access, referenceable storage locations (Gäde *et al.*, 2021). The repository should be findable and accessible. It is important that the best repository is chosen for the dataset in question (i.e., some repositories have a limit on the size of dataset that can be uploaded, or specialises in datasets of a specific type) (Corpas *et al.*, 2018). The repository should be citable, which will not only help track provenance and Intellectual Property, but also act as an incentive to researchers to share their data (Gäde *et al.*, 2021).

Incentives

Incentives can help encourage data providers to share their data, data users to reuse data and all stakeholders to follow best practice. Gäde *et al.*, (2021) suggest reward systems that are developed by the community (e.g., the use of badges by some journals). Challenge prizes, such as the Data-Centric engineering program (ATI) and Lloyd's Register Safety Accelerator, could provide incentives for researchers (Dodds *et al.*, 2020). Ensuring that data is shared in a way that it can be cited can also help incentivise researchers (Corpas *et al.*, 2018)

FAIRness

Many of the selected papers referred to the FAIR principles or even used them as an evaluation framework (e.g., Corpas *et al.*, 2018; Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018). Any general principles should consider the inclusion, or at least the relation, to the FAIR principles.

3.2. Other principles to consider

The following five topics were not identified as common themes but should be considered if developing any general principles designed to be agnostic to sector and discipline.

- Research and publications should be shared promptly (Callaghan, 2020). This helps foster innovation and knowledge transfer whilst reducing the chances of repeating existing research.
- Opening and sharing data unlocks value. Linking and combining data with other datasets can unlock further value. However, linking with other datasets can also lead to reidentification of deidentified data (Cole *et al.*, 2021). Permission should be sought if a recipient wishes to link data with other data (Cole *et al.*, 2021).
- There is not just an increased demand for the skills of data scientists but for a much wider group of users to be data literate. A data sharing ecosystem requires the development of data literacy and skills. This could be done by embedding them in higher education curriculums and professional transient courses (Dodds *et al.*, 2020).
- It is important that data can be found. The machine-readability of the data and metadata should be maximised to ensure findability and interoperability (Corpas *et al.*, 2018).
- The FAIR principles focus on the machine-readability of a dataset. Since machines are unlikely to be able to fully understand and process digital assets, a human will always be involved in the process in some way (Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018). Different challenges are faced by humans and machines in discovering and retrieving datasets that are relevant (e.g., ability to use semantics, interpret contextual clues vs speed) (Tenenbaum and Blach, 2018). These differences should be taken into consideration when developing principles for data sharing and data reuse.

4. Role of Policy

Each set of principles that have been considered in this paper addresses policy in some way. The common themes where policies played a role include planning, documentation, governance, stewarding and incentives. However, policy to promote data reuse is not a sufficient mechanism on its own (Pasquetto, Randles, & Borgman, 2017). Practical guidance must be available in the form of suitable methodologies and frameworks. Further work is needed to establish whether such guidance could be delivered that is sector agnostic.

Just as researchers must be aware of any changes in the legal and regulatory environments (Dodds *et al.*, 2020), policy and regulation must adapt as new technologies and

uses of data emerges. Regulators and policy makers must also adapt to ensure they understand the role data will play. Principles and guidelines could be developed that helped ensure a proactive approach to establishing policy, rather than reacting (e.g., to new technologies).

Data reuse must be economically and socially beneficial if it is to become normal practice. The cultural barriers must be overcome as well as the practical or technical challenges. The creation of a data ecosystem where data reuse is expected requires an established data culture that considers how data should be captured, designed, and documented to ensure reuse (Wood and Bordoloi, 2023). There is a need to develop a culture of trusted data sharing, which will require coordinated action from a range of stakeholders (Dodds *et al.*, 2020), including policy makers and regulators.

5. Conclusion

The ability to reuse data could deliver better value from the initial investment made by allowing an organisation to use their resources more efficiently potentially saving time and money. This paper focuses on a selection of principles that have been suggested as necessary to facilitate an ecosystem where data is reused by addressing the research question how do the different sets of principles suggested compare and what role does policy play? A comparison of the principles has identified nine common themes and an additional five principles that would be applicable to a wider audience than they were originally intended. When combined, these could be used as the basis for a set of principles that are agnostic to sector or the type of data. Further work will see researchers, practitioners and policy makers work together to develop a set of sector agnostic principles, and practical guidelines, that will facilitate a data sharing ecosystem.

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